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Report on **Milestone 21**

Protocol of laboratory processing of DBSS data

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Abstract: This report documents the achievement of the milestone 21 of the SSHOC project, which was to document the laboratory processing of DBSS in a protocol. A subsample of 8000 dried blood spot samples (DBSS) was processed. Then, validation experiments were carried out now allowing the correction of assay results for field-caused influences.

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1. Introduction

In cross-national population studies measuring health and life style factors in ageing by self-reported information is challenging due to several difficulties, such as socio-cultural differences in reporting style, social desirability and access to health care etc. Moreover, in older people a new health condition may remain unrecognised by sharing the same symptoms as an existing disease, or by having symptoms that are interpreted as a result of ageing per se. Also, cognitive decline or depressive symptoms may affect correct recollection. SHARE seeks to optimise the self-reported health information by carrying out objective measurements and assessments, resulting in harmonised unbiased results in the health of Europeans across diverse cultures and national institutions. As one of such objective health measurements, SHARE has collected ca 27.000 dried blood spot (DBS) samples in 12 different countries during its field collection in 2015. As SHARE provides free data access for all collected survey data to scientific researchers, it also aims to give access to these dried blood spot data. However, such innovative biomedical data pose new challenges to data processing, and demand new ways of data access. For the DBS data dissemination, we preview the following steps:

1. Processing of the DBS in specialised laboratories to extract the health indicators of interest for SHARE, controlling for the effect of fieldwork conditions (primary analyses)
2. Design of ethics guidelines and special data protection needs for providing scientific access to DBS data in the setting of an international survey
3. Construction of a DBS database consisting of individual records for SHARE panel members with variables that represent the health indicator outcomes of the primary laboratory analysis for each panel member, as well as meta-data
4. Linkage of the DBS database to the SHARE survey panel data into a complete dataset for scientific use
5. Design of an operational procedure to provide scientific users access to the complete DBS-Survey dataset, following the ethics and data protection guidelines of step 2
6. Release of a test case of a limited part of the DBS-Survey dataset for scientific use, evaluation by means of a usability test
7. Improvement of the access procedure on the basis of the test results
8. Release of final DBS-Survey dataset for scientific use (secondary analyses)

Steps 7 and 8 are out of the scope of the SSHOC project, whereas steps 2, 5, and 6 will result in deliverables D5.1, D5.2 and D5.4 of the project. In addition, steps 1 and 6 will be described in the milestones M21 and M23, respectively.

2. Description of the Milestone

2.1. Role of the Milestone

Milestone 21 is related to step 1 in the process of providing access for scientific researchers to biomedical data in a survey context. As described in the introduction, the first step for the SHARE DBS data consists of the primary analysis of the DBS in specialised laboratories. As the outcomes of this analysis is the fundament for the value of the open-access data in the final step of the process above, it is essential that the analysis process and decisions are well documented, and that all information about fieldwork conditions and other meta-data are available. The milestone is strongly related to deliverable D5.1, the guidelines for ethics considerations in making biomedical survey data FAIR, because the laboratory processing protocol is the documentation that is needed to make the DBS data re-usable (the R in FAIR).

2.2. Means of verification

To make the SHARE DBS data re-usable for scientific researchers, the meta-data and all control and validation analyses are documented in the DBS laboratory processing protocol, which forms the basis of this milestone. Table 1 documents how many usable good-quality blood spot samples resulted from the original number of collected DBS samples, and the steps in between. This meta-data is essential to understand the process of selection of final usable cases.

The collection, storage, first analyses and validation for field conditions are documented in: Collection of Dried Blood Spots in SHARE: From implementation to blood-marker analyses. Börsch-Supan, M. et al. (2020) forthcoming. The paper will be accessible on the SHARE website: www.share-project.org.

So far, SHARE has carried out analyses for diabetes (HbA1c) and cardiovascular disease risk markers (total and HDL-cholesterol, Triglycerides, CRP, Cystatin C) and for total haemoglobin indicating anaemia and frailty in 8000 randomly chosen SHARE DBS samples. Moreover, ca. 15.000 DBS samples were analysed for five cytokine markers, three growth factors (IL-16, IL-8, IL-12/23, IL-18, MCP1; BDNF, VEGF, EGF) and the apolipoproteins ApoE4 and ApoJ (Clusterin).

Biomarker values analysed from field-collected dried blood spot samples cannot be taken at face value, because dried blood spot (DBS) samples differ from standard blood samples, mainly in two ways. First, they contain all blood components including cells as opposed to plasma usually used for standard blood analyses. Second, it is dried, not wet blood as in standard samples. Furthermore, in case of field-collected samples, the values measured in such DBS samples are influenced by varying fieldwork conditions, such as drying time, outside temperature or shipment time.

Therefore, SHARE is conducting specific validation studies to evaluate the effect of such conditions on the results of marker analyses and to develop a conversion equation to re-calculate the raw DBS values into biomarker values that we would have expected for blood collected and analysed using standard laboratory methods. For this purpose, a new DBS samples was created from volunteers and simulated fieldwork conditions

in a controlled way (e.g. varying drying times or temperature exposures). Both validation experiments 1) for the diabetes and cardiovascular disease markers 2) for the cytokine markers are completed.

Table 1. Number of DBS samples per country, across four steps of pre-laboratory processing.

	Total number of DBS samples collected	Number of "complete"¹ DBS samples	Number of "complete" DBS samples containing blood²	"Complete" DBS samples with at least one good-quality blood spot³
Belgium	3690	3604	3484	3166
Switzerland	2132	2095	2051	1953
Germany	3147	3124	3095	2872
Denmark	2861	2842	2833	2715
Estonia	3683	3670	3652	3285
Spain	1827	1771	1754	1462
France	578	552	507	429
Greece	807	736	735	580
Israel	1073	1030	1030	821
Italy	2175	2153	2121	1839
Sweden	3013	2907	2893	2600
Slovenia	2242	2221	2196	2101
Total	27 228	26 705	26 351	23 823

Source: SHARE data release 7.0.0 and internal data on DBS samples; 1 – a sample is considered complete (and only then it is intended for laboratory analysis) if it is linkable to a SHARE interview dataset, and if informed written consent by the respondent is available; 2 – Not all samples do contain blood material, because some elderly people do not easily bleed and, hence, we received a number of "empty" sample cards; 3 – smeared or overlapping blood spots cannot be used for laboratory analysis.

3. Conclusions and next steps

The validation experiments were a necessary step after the analyses of 8000 filed samples. SHARE created conversion equations for each marker. Now it is possible to convert the direct DBS blood values into values comparable with conventionally gained blood values, like venous blood drawn in a lab. The analyses of the remaining ca. 16.000 samples for HbA1c, total and HDL-cholesterol, triglycerides, CRP, and Cystatin C will resume in January 2020. The assay time (processing the samples in the lab) is estimated to take about one year. The project is still on track, neither reorganisation nor changes are planned or necessary.

This milestone provides the documentation and information of the first step for the SHARE DBS data: The primary analyses of the DBS in specialised laboratories. The milestone thus is the basis for reaching the deliverable D5.2, the data access protocol for DBSS data linked to survey data, which represents the steps 4 and 5 in the process described in the introduction, and towards reaching the user-friendly test data release which is D5.4 and is written in step 6 of the process above.

4. References

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